

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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ANALYSIS OF THE CAUSES OF RECURRENCE AFTER RADICAL TRACHELECTOMY IN PATIENTS WITH INVASIVE CERVICAL CANCER**Mamedov U.S., Nurov J.R., Abdurahimova Y.A.**

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Resume. Objective of the study. To conduct a systematic analysis of the data available in the current literature regarding the recurrence rate after radical trachelectomy in patients with invasive cervical cancer, the timing of recurrence, the locations, treatment options, and to assess the risk factors for recurrence depending on the surgical access approach. Materials and Methods. The review includes data from foreign and domestic articles found in PubMed on this topic, published over the last 5 years. Results. Radical trachelectomy is the standard surgical treatment for early-stage invasive cervical cancer in young women who wish to preserve reproductive function. The oncological safety of radical trachelectomy has been proven in many studies, and clear criteria for patient selection for radical trachelectomy via various approaches (vaginal, abdominal, laparoscopic, robot-assisted) have been developed. However, in some patients, disease recurrence occurs. Since this surgery is performed infrequently in various oncological institutions and the accumulation of data is slow, the analysis of treatment results in small numbers of patients often does not allow authors to make definitive conclusions. The current analysis includes over 40 studies. Conclusion. The data obtained from the analysis confirm the need for a strict selection of patients with invasive cervical cancer for organ-preserving treatment to achieve optimal oncological outcomes.

Keywords: organ-preserving treatment for cervical cancer, radical trachelectomy, oncological outcomes, recurrences.

ИНВАЗИВ БАЧАДОН БЎЙНИ САРАТОНИДА РАДИКАЛ ТРАХЕЛЭКТОМИЯДАН КЕЙИНГИ РЕЦИДИВЛАР САБАБЛАРИНИ ТАҲЛИЛЛАШ**Мамедов У.С., Нуров Ж.Р., Абдурахимова Ё.А.**

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Резюме. Тадқиқот мақсади. Инвазив бўлган бачадон бўйни саратони билан оғриган беморларда радикал трахелэктомия ўтказилгандан кейин қайталанишларнинг юзага келиш частотасини, уларнинг пайдо бўлиш вақтлари, локализацияси ва даволаш вариантларини ҳамда жарроҳлик кириши йўли билан боғлиқ бўлган қайталаниш хавф факторларини тизимли таҳлил қилиш. Материал ва методлар. Ушбу шарҳда сўнгги 5 йил ичида PubMed маълумотлар базасида ушбу мавзуга оид хорижий ва маҳаллий мақолалардан олинган маълумотлар киритилган. Натижалар. Радикал трахелэктомия — ёш аёлларда, репродуктив функцияни сақлаб қолишни хоҳлаган ҳолда, эрта босқичдаги инвазив бачадон бўйни саратонининг стандарт жарроҳлик даволаш усули ҳисобланади. Радикал трахелэктомия онкологик хавфсизлиги кўплаб тадқиқотлар билан исботланган ва турли кириши йўллари (вагинал, абдоминал, лапароскопик, робот ёрдамида) орқали радикал трахелэктомия учун беморларни танлашнинг аниқ мезонлари ишлаб чиқилган. Шунга қарамай, баъзи беморларда касалликнинг қайталаниши юзага келади. Ушбу операция турли онкологик муассасаларда камдан-кам бажарилиши ва материалнинг тўпланиши секин кечиши сабабли, кичик сонли беморлар бўйича даволаш натижаларини таҳлил қилиш кўпинча муаллифларга яқин хулосалар чиқаришига имкон бермайди. Ҳозирги таҳлилга 40 дан ортиқ тадқиқотлар киритилган. Хулоса. Ўтказилган таҳлил натижалари, онкологик натижаларни оптималлаштириши мақсадида инвазив бачадон бўйни саратони билан оғриган беморлар учун органни сақловчи даволашни қатъий танлаш зарурлигини тасдиқлайди.

Калит сўзлар: бачадон бўйни саратонининг органни сақловчи даволаш, радикал трахелэктомия, онкологик натижалар, қайталанишлар.

АНАЛИЗ ПРИЧИН РЕЦИДИВА ПОСЛЕ РАДИКАЛЬНОЙ ТРАХЕЛЭКТОМИИ У ПАЦИЕНТОК С ИНВАЗИВНЫМ РАКОМ ШЕЙКИ МАТКИ**Мамедов У.С., Нуров Ж.Р., Абдурахимова Ё.А.**

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Резюме. Цель исследования. Провести системный анализ имеющихся в текущей литературе данных о частоте рецидивов после радикальной трахэктомии у пациенток с инвазивным раком шейки матки, времени возникновения рецидивов, местах их локализации, вариантах лечения и оценить

факторы риска рецидива в зависимости от метода хирургического доступа. Материалы и методы. Обзор включает данные зарубежных и отечественных статей, найденных в PubMed по данной теме, опубликованных за последние 5 лет. Результаты. Радикальная трахектомия является стандартным хирургическим методом лечения рака шейки матки на ранних стадиях у молодых женщин, желающих сохранить репродуктивную функцию. Онкологическая безопасность радикальной трахектомии была доказана во многих исследованиях, и разработаны четкие критерии отбора пациенток для радикальной трахектомии через различные подходы (вагинальный, абдоминальный, лапароскопический, роботизированный). Однако у некоторых пациенток происходит рецидив заболевания. Так как эта операция выполняется нечасто в различных онкологических учреждениях, а накопление данных происходит медленно, анализ результатов лечения у небольших групп пациенток часто не позволяет авторам делать окончательные выводы. В данный анализ включены данные более 40 исследований. Заключение. Данные, полученные в результате анализа, подтверждают необходимость строгого отбора пациенток с инвазивным раком шейки матки для органосохраняющего лечения с целью достижения оптимальных онкологических результатов.

Ключевые слова: органосохраняющее лечение рака шейки матки, радикальная трахектомия, онкологические результаты, рецидивы.

Introduction. Cervical cancer is a common oncological disease among women of reproductive age. Every year, more than half a million new cases of cervical cancer are registered worldwide [1]. In 2018, Russia registered 17,766 new cases of cervical cancer, with 4,076 of them in women aged 20–39 years [2]. At the time of diagnosis, the issue of reproductive function preservation remains open for many women. The standard surgical treatment for early-stage cervical cancer is radical hysterectomy and pelvic lymphadenectomy, which excludes fertility preservation. The idea of organ-preserving treatment for early-stage cervical cancer was first proposed in the 1950s by scientists F. Novak and E. Aburel [3, 4]. It was not until three decades later, in 1986, that D. Dargent and colleagues performed the first vaginal radical trachelectomy (VRT) with laparoscopic pelvic lymphadenectomy, which later became known as the Dargent operation [5]. In 1997, J. Smith and colleagues first described the technique of radical abdominal trachelectomy (RAT) [6]. The introduction of laparoscopic access into organ-preserving treatment for cervical cancer occurred gradually. In 2005, D. Cibula and colleagues presented the first description of total radical laparoscopic trachelectomy (RLT) [7]. In 2008, L. Chuang and F. Nezhat published data on the first robot-assisted radical trachelectomy and pelvic lymphadenectomy [8].

Currently, radical trachelectomy can be performed in reproductive-age patients using various approaches: vaginal, abdominal, laparoscopic, and robot-assisted. A thorough selection of patients for organ-preserving treatment is extremely important. According to research, oncological outcomes of radical trachelectomy using various approaches, when selection criteria are followed, are comparable to those of radical hysterectomy for tumors with similar primary characteristics. The oncological safety of radical trachelectomy has been demonstrated in many retrospective and prospective studies, and randomized trials on this topic are not feasible. Numerous original studies and several systematic reviews evaluating oncological outcomes after various types of radical trachelectomies have been published in foreign literature. However, there are only a few publications in domestic literature on this topic.

We conducted an analysis of global literature data on the recurrences of invasive cervical cancer after radical trachelectomies performed using different approaches. The literature search was carried out in the PubMed, MedScape, and Elibrary databases. The analysis includes the most significant publications in English and Russian from 2000 to 2020, excluding case reports.

Radical Vaginal Trachelectomy. The first analysis of recurrences of cervical cancer after organ-preserving treatment was presented in the study by the founder of VRT, D. Dargent, and colleagues in 2000 [9]. Among 47 patients who underwent VRT, recurrence developed in two patients (4.3%). According to the authors, the recurrence rate was higher in the group with non-squamous cell histology: 1 out of 8 (12.5%) compared to 1 out of 39 (2.6%). Additionally, recurrence rates were higher in the group with vascular invasion: 2 out of 13 (15.4%) compared to 0 out of 34, and in the group with tumors larger than 2 cm: 2 out of 7 (28.6%) compared to 0 out of 40 ($p < 0.001$). It was already evident that a tumor size larger than 2 cm is a leading risk factor for recurrence after VRT.

In 2007, M. Beiner and colleagues published the first systematic review, which included oncological results from 7 major studies (548 patients), analyzing recurrences after vaginal radical trachelectomy [10]. With a median follow-up of 47 months, recurrences occurred in 5.1% of patients. About 40% of recurrent tumors were localized in the parametrium and pelvic wall. The authors linked this to insufficient volume of parametrectomy during VRT. When analyzing risk factors for recurrence, it was shown that for tumors larger

than 2 cm, recurrences occurred in 17% of patients, compared to 2% for tumors <2 cm. Therefore, it was shown that the risk of recurrence significantly increases for tumors larger than 2 cm, which later became a contraindication for performing vaginal radical trachelectomy. The analysis of lymphovascular invasion (LVI) showed that only 28% of patients had LVI after VRT, and 12% of them experienced recurrence, compared to 2% of recurrences in patients without LVI ($p = 0.001$). Several studies have shown that the presence of only LVI, without other adverse prognostic factors, does not affect recurrence-free survival, and thus should not be an absolute contraindication for VRT [11, 12]. Nevertheless, patients should be informed about the increased risk of recurrence. When analyzing histological types, adenocarcinoma or adenosquamous carcinoma were diagnosed in 34% of patients, but the authors of the review did not find an increased risk of recurrence in this group.

In a large original prospective study by Mangler et al., 2014, the authors specifically studied the structure of recurrences and the risk factors for their development, evaluating the treatment outcomes of 320 patients with tumors up to 2 cm in size after radical vaginal trachelectomy (RVT). Neuroendocrine and other rare histological forms were not included in the study. The recurrence rate was 3.13%, and the average time until recurrence was 26.1 months (ranging from 3 to 108 months). Half of the patients died from disease progression, with an average of 8.8 months (4–15 months) after recurrence was detected. The other half were in remission at the time of publication, following treatment for the recurrence of the disease (radical hysterectomy and/or chemoradiotherapy). The localization of recurrences was primarily central—the cervical stump in 6 out of 10 patients; in 3 patients, recurrences were found in the pelvic wall, and in 1 patient, the recurrence was in the cervical stump along with distant metastases. In the recurrence group, 20% of the patients had poorly differentiated tumors (G3), lymphovascular invasion (LVI) was found in 40%, and parametral invasion was 0%. The study did not identify significant risk factors for recurrence after RVT in patients with tumors up to 2 cm [12].

We analyzed data from 16 large published studies (1617 patients), 15 of which reported 69 recurrences after RVT (Table 1). The time to progression ranged from 3 to 108 months. The histological form of the tumor was squamous cell carcinoma in 36% of patients ($n = 25$), adenocarcinoma in 36% ($n = 25$), and adenosquamous carcinoma in 5.8% of patients ($n = 4$). One patient had a neuroendocrine tumor, and in 14 cases, histological data were not available. The degree of differentiation was tracked in only 40 of the 69 patients, with the following distribution: G1 – 2.9%, G2 – 30.4%, and G3 – 24.6%. Data on LVI were available for 40 patients, with vascular invasion identified in 19 patients.

The localization of recurrent tumors was analyzed in all the cases. The analysis of recurrence localization showed that 37.7% ($n = 26$) of recurrences were located in the remaining part of the cervix. In the parametrium, 11 recurrences were identified (15.9%), 4 of which were from a prospective study by Cao et al. (2013), where 31.1% of patients had tumors sized 2-4 cm, and in 5 of 7 patients with recurrence, the tumor size exceeded 2 cm [13]. Among the described regional recurrences, 11 were localized in the pelvic wall, and 2 in the pelvic lymph nodes. In 6 patients, distant metastases were found. In 6 patients, recurrences were simultaneously identified in the cervix and in the parametrium, pelvic wall, ovary, or beyond the pelvic area (para-aortic, supraclavicular lymph nodes, liver). A recurrent tumor in the ovary was described in one patient, in combination with a recurrence in the cervix.

After treatment for cervical cancer recurrence, 37.7% of patients died from disease progression ($n = 26$), while the remaining patients were alive with no signs of progression at the time of publication. Thus, the average recurrence rate after RVT was 4.3%, and mortality from disease progression was about 1.6%.

Radical Abdominal Trachelectomy (RAT). The oncological outcomes of radical abdominal trachelectomy (RAT) are comparable to those of radical abdominal hysterectomy, both for tumors up to 2 cm and for tumors in the 2-4 cm range. It should be noted that the more radical approach of RAT, compared to RVT, was the reason for applying this version of trachelectomy for tumors larger than 2 cm. Studies on the risk factors for recurrence after radical abdominal trachelectomy have been conducted in many research papers.

The first publication evaluating the oncological outcomes of RAT was by L. Ungar et al. In 2005, the authors presented the results of a prospective analysis that included 30 patients, 9 of whom had tumors larger than 2 cm, and 5 patients were diagnosed with stage IB2 disease. With a median follow-up of 47 months after RAT, recurrence was not detected in any of the patients [27].

In the study by Nichio et al., 2009, recurrences occurred in 6 out of 61 patients (9.8%). Five of these 6 recurrences developed in a group of 13 patients with tumors larger than 2 cm in diameter. In one patient, the histological form of the tumor was adenocarcinoma. Upon analyzing their data, the authors concluded that tumor size greater than 2 cm in diameter, lymphovascular invasion (LVI), and adenocarcinoma could be factors contributing to an increased risk of recurrence after radical abdominal trachelectomy (RAT) [28].

In 2013, Linter et al. presented data from the analysis of 45 patients with stage IB1-IB2 cervical cancer and tumors larger than 2 cm in diameter. The authors demonstrated that radical abdominal trachelectomy (RAT) is oncologically safe for patients in this group. The five-year disease-free survival rate was 87.1%, and the overall survival rate was 93.5% [29].

In the domestic literature, the largest experience with radical abdominal trachelectomy (RAT) is represented by the P.A. Herzen Moscow Research Institute of Oncology. In 2017, they published the results of 79 RAT cases from 2005 to 2016. With a median follow-up of 80 months, recurrences were observed in 7 (8.9%) patients: in 5 cases, tumor growth continued between 4 to 10 months after surgery, and in 2 patients, late recurrences were noted at 50 and 62 months following organ-preserving treatment. The most frequent locations of recurrent tumors were the parametria along the pelvic wall, para-aortic lymph nodes, and the neocervix. The disease-free survival rate in this group was 91.1%, and the overall survival rate was 95% [24].

In 2017, K. Morkhov and colleagues presented the experience of the N.N. Blokhin National Medical Research Center of Oncology of the Ministry of Health of Russia. RAT was performed on 28 patients with tumor sizes ranging from 0.4 to 6.0 cm. With a median follow-up of 54 months, disease progression occurred in one patient (3.6%), with metastasis in the external cervical os, left parametrial space, and para-rectal lymph nodes and ovary. The patient underwent chemoradiotherapy according to a radical program with partial effect. At the time of publication, the patient was receiving palliative chemotherapy due to further disease progression [30].

Analyzing the data from world literature, the recurrence rate after RAT varies from 0.7% to 12.9%, with an average of 4%. The variability in disease-free survival data after RAT is most likely due to the relatively small number of observations in different studies. The surgeon's experience, which determines the extent of parametrial tissue removal, may also be a factor.

We analyzed 10 international and 5 domestic studies (Table 2). Only patients after radical abdominal trachelectomy who did not receive neoadjuvant or adjuvant therapy were evaluated. The follow-up period ranged from 3 to 148 months. Among 1144 patients after RAT, recurrences occurred in 4% of patients ($n = 46$). The time to recurrence varied from 3 to 62 months. In most cases (54.3%), recurrences developed within the first 2 years of observation, while 11% of recurrences occurred at later times—41 to 62 months.

The histological form of the recurrent tumor could be traced in only 17 patients. Among them, 11 had squamous cell carcinoma (24%), 6 had adenocarcinoma (13%), and 1 had clear cell carcinoma. The localization of the recurrent tumor was traced in 31 patients. Local recurrences (vaginal cuff, uterine body, cervix) were found in 13 patients; in one case, a local recurrence in the cervix was combined with metastatic ovarian involvement; recurrences localized in the pelvis (pelvic wall and pelvic lymph nodes) were found in 9 cases; in the parametria, there was one case. Distant recurrences were diagnosed in 7 patients, with ovarian metastasis in 2 cases: one had a recurrence in the pelvic wall, and the other had metastasis in the retroperitoneal lymph nodes. Both patients had squamous cell carcinoma. Among 12 patients with available data on tumor size, 10 had tumors larger than 2.0 cm. Lymphovascular invasion was observed in 7 out of 10 patients; data for the others could not be traced.

It is known that 21.7% of patients ($n = 10$) died from disease progression.

Radical Laparoscopic Trachelectomy (RLT): With the development of laparoscopic surgery, minimally invasive methods have been actively introduced into oncological gynecology practice. However, publications on laparoscopic trachelectomy are scarce, with only a few studies involving more than 10 patients. The largest studies are by Ebisawa et al. (2013) and Park et al. (2014).

In the retrospective study by Ebisawa et al. (2013) involving 56 patients with tumor sizes less than 25 mm, recurrence developed in one patient (1.8%), localized in the right obturator fossa. The patient died from disease progression 2 years after surgery [48].

The study by Park et al. (2014) represents the largest prospective study organized by the Asan Gynecologic Cancer Group in South Korea. The study analyzed the results of 79 patients after RLT, examining the risk factors for recurrence. The median follow-up was 44 months (3-105 months). Recurrences occurred in 11% of patients ($n = 9$), and one patient died from disease progression (1.3%). Univariate analysis did not reveal any dependence of disease-free survival on age, histological type, or lymphovascular invasion. However, tumor size greater than 2 cm and invasion depth greater than half of the cervical wall were associated with a decreased disease-free survival rate. The recurrence rate was 6% for tumors smaller than 2 cm and 20.7% for tumors larger than 2 cm [49].

In the domestic literature, data on RLT are available only in a few studies.

In 2017, Shevchuk et al. presented the results of organ-preserving treatment using radical laparoscopic trachelectomy (RLT) in 19 patients, of which 7 patients had tumors larger than 2 cm. In one patient (5.3%),

continued tumor growth was detected at the vaginal cuff 7 months after surgery, for which the patient underwent chemoradiation therapy. The patient is alive without signs of disease progression.

We analyzed 6 international and 3 domestic studies (Table 3). A total of 257 patients were included, and 12 recurrences of disease after RLT were reported. The average recurrence rate was 4.7%. The analysis of these results showed that 66.7% of recurrent tumors localized in the small pelvis, either at the pelvic wall or in the pelvic lymph nodes, all of which were histologically diagnosed as squamous cell carcinoma. Initially, tumors larger than 2 cm were present in 50% of patients, and stromal invasion greater than 1/2 was observed in 41.7% of patients. Adenocarcinoma was diagnosed in one patient, and adenosquamous carcinoma in two. In 5 patients (41.7%), the tumor had a low degree of differentiation.

The results suggest that RLT is oncologically safe for patients with tumors up to 2 cm in size and with stromal invasion of the cervix less than 1/2.

Despite the results of the aforementioned studies, since the publication of the randomized LACC (Laparoscopic approach in Cervical Cancer) study, laparoscopic access is not recommended for performing radical hysterectomy in cervical cancer due to poorer outcomes in terms of disease-free survival and overall survival. For known reasons, conducting a similar randomized study in the context of radical trachelectomy is not possible. Therefore, the effectiveness of various types of radical trachelectomy can only be evaluated based on retrospective and prospective studies. Recent studies indicate the possibility of safely applying video-endoscopic surgery in organ-preserving treatment for cervical cancer.

However, for performing radical laparoscopic trachelectomy, strict patient selection is required according to classical criteria:

1. Reproductive age of the patient, a desire to preserve reproductive function, and the absence of infertility.
2. Squamous, glandular, or adenosquamous histological tumor type (rare forms of cervical cancer, such as neuroendocrine carcinoma, carcinosarcoma, and others, which indicate an unfavorable oncological prognosis, are contraindications for organ-preserving treatment).
3. IA1 stage with the presence of lymphovascular invasion, IA2, IB1 stages with tumor sizes up to 2 cm, with invasion up to 1/2 of the cervical wall thickness, and no spread to the upper third of the cervical canal.
4. Absence of signs of metastatic lymph node involvement and the presence of distant metastases.
5. Possibility of strict dynamic monitoring.
6. Appropriate surgeon preparation.

Optimal conditions for performing radical laparoscopic trachelectomy (RLT) are created after conization of the cervix, and RLT is performed in conditions where no tumor tissue remains in the cervix. In such cases, there is no biological basis for potential tumor dissemination as a result of using minimally invasive techniques.

Robot-assisted radical trachelectomy (RART). Literature on radical robotic trachelectomy is extremely limited. The only prospective study was presented by Johansen et al. in 2016 [54]. With a median follow-up of 24 months, no recurrences of the disease were noted after 48 RARTs. In the largest retrospective study by Vieira et al., the analysis of 22 radical robotic trachelectomies showed no recurrences of disease with a median follow-up of 25 months [40].

Treatment of recurrences after radical trachelectomy. The choice of treatment for recurrent cervical cancer after radical trachelectomy depends on the extent of the tumor process. In the presence of distant metastases, the prognosis is unfavorable, and patients undergo chemotherapy, sometimes combined with radiation therapy in the presence of disease in the pelvic area. For local recurrences, treatment options vary from surgical intervention (radical hysterectomy) to chemoradiation therapy, depending on the location and size of the recurrent tumor. According to combined data, the survival rates of patients with diagnosed recurrence of cervical cancer after radical vaginal trachelectomy (RVT) were 62.3%, after radical abdominal trachelectomy (RAT) were 71.7%, and after radical laparoscopic trachelectomy (RLT) were 91.7%.

Conclusion. Although randomized studies evaluating the oncological outcomes of radical trachelectomies are lacking, the analysis of recurrence causes indicates that the most significant risk factors are tumor size (>2 cm), the depth of stromal invasion (greater than 1/2 the thickness of the cervical wall), and the presence of lymphovascular invasion. Performing radical trachelectomy in the presence of these risk factors is possible; however, patients should be warned about the increased risk of recurrence, including progression in the form of dissemination of the oncological process. The choice of surgical approach should be made in strict consideration of the risk factors and depending on the surgeon's level of expertise.

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